

Intelligent ASVs to explore water bodies and support HABs detection, prediction and early warning

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Abstract

Harmful Algae Blooms (HABs) are dynamic biological processes that occur inside many water bodies and become visible as they expand into the water surface. They should be anticipated/detected as soon as possible, to warn the authorities about dangerous situations. Early warning systems in use today, are not enough to capture HAB temporal-space evolution, because their probes, placed at fixed locations, cannot provide the quantity and distributed data required to understand what is happening. Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASVs, a kind of robotized boats) can be used instead as mobile sensor platforms to take measurements of the variables of interest at different locations and depths of the water body. Our research goes one step beyond and aims to develop an Artificial Intelligent aLERT (AILERT-HAB) system based on intelligent ASVs capable of deciding where and how to take measurements for building models that predict HABs evolution and alert the authorities about them. Our ASVs are equipped with on-board computers and software designed for mixed-initiative work, which lets human operators intervene when desired, while ASVs usually function autonomously as a fleet, performing coordinated exploration tasks supported by different principles. For instance, these tasks can be achieved from a systematic water covering/monitoring perspective, by pre-planning the ASV and probe trajectories using the information provided by the simulations and/or the probability distribution of the HABs, or with data-driven controllers that adapt the ASVs displacements to the information extracted in real-time from the measurements taken by its on-board probes. During this paper, we will provide an overall view of our system, with details of the already-developed elements.

Keywords: HAB early warning, Autonomous Surface Vehicles, water exploration algorithms

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Introduction

Every year, Harmful Algae Blooms (HABs) develop on inland waters, and some of them (e.g., cyanobacteria blooms) generate toxins. Moreover, the evolution of algae population and their physiological state in reservoirs, lakes, and rivers, follows a spatio-temporal process, difficult to monitor and predict. Hence, it is urgent to devise early warning systems that incorporate new means to localize and understand better the biological phenomena that originate the HABs.

In Spain, where there are about 350 reservoirs (some of them among the ten largest in Europe) and convenient weather conditions for the HABs, they are a noteworthy problem. Here, data acquisition stations are being used to monitor the water conditions from fixed locations, with limited results. Besides, people on board floating vehicles are sent for sampling and measuring sporadically or when suspicious HABs activity has been detected. Both solutions provide scarce information, not enough to predict new HABs.

Our proposal is to use Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASVs, a kind of robotized boats) for automatic data acquisition. They should operate in an intelligent manner to get to the regions of interest at proper times, to maximize the probability of getting relevant measurements (or samples). This is not straightforward, since HABs can move horizontally, as well as up and down, according to the wind, currents, diffusion, and thermal stratification.

This proposal is being explored in two research projects. The key idea of the first, named AMPBAS (Automatic Monitoring

of Pollutants in dammed waters using Biosensors and ASVs), is to provide simulation support, complemented with intelligent historical data analysis, for guiding the navigation decisions taken by the ASVs, to improve the chances of collecting successfully located measurements. The idea has already been developed and tested under simulations and remains to be experimentally evaluated in real-world scenarios. The second project, named IA-GES-BLOOM-CM (towards a comprehensive system for the alert and management of cyanobacteria blooms in inland waters), is in preliminary steps and involves the synergic collaboration of biologists, and experts in robotics and automation. Its purpose is to develop an early warning system, that involves fleets of intelligent ASVs, which act as nodes of an Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructure, to help water managers to anticipate cyanobacteria blooms. Interest in the results of both projects comes from companies and institutions with responsibilities in drinking water supply, and authorities linked to large (national) parks, wild-life support, and recreational facilities.

Material and Methods

Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASVs)

A typical example of ASV would be a boat with an on-board electronic control system, which governs the boat motion, according with algorithms and some specifications of the desired boat behaviour. Besides, their onboard sensors, including cameras for instance, can be used for taking measurements about its surroundings. Finally, usual designs of the boat come in the form of catamarans, trimarans, or mono hulls.

Our experience on ASVs development and automation starts in 1997. Since then, different ASVs have been built in our facilities for several purposes: including boom towing, harbour surveillance, or research on ASVs swarms. Our ASVs use electric propulsion to move fast, or slow, depending on application. Their size also depends on the research targets, ranging from small (around 60 cm long) to moderate size (1.5m) and larger (4m long).

Our ASVs carry on-board control systems that we develop and build. Currently, they are based on a powerful-enough digital processor with convenient inputs and outputs for robotic control application. We also develop the control software to be free to select the functional endowment of the ASV, for present and future applications. At present, we have programmed a mixed initiative for the ASV control, to let ASVs decide autonomously where to move (or which actions to execute) and to let human operators take the ASV control from distance when required. Lastly, each ASV has a digital radio link for interaction with a supervision station, and a standard radio control channel for direct human intervention.

For AMPBAS and IA-GES-BLOOM-CM, moderate-size ASVs have been selected, easy to transport and deploy on the field, cheap-enough for many types of water bodies, straightforward to be used without a high-level expertise.

Two types of ASVs, as the ones presented in figures 1 and 2, are under development and testing. Both can navigate on shallow waters. One carries sensors for measurements near the epilimnion. The other has a sort of crane,

to handle up and down, for a depth of several meters, a multi-parameter probe. Both types of ASVs are medium size (around 120 cm long; less than 30 kg weight) to facilitate its transportation and deployment on places difficult to reach (e.g., the shore can be rocky, without flat access). It is also worth noting that at present, the ASVs use LiPo batteries. In the future, its power system will incorporate solar panels and a battery management intelligent system to increment the ASV autonomy.

Fig. 1. ASV with camera and sensors.

Fig. 2. ASV with crane for multiparameter probe.

Besides, the ASVs motion specification-scripting framework is being incrementally developed and tested. Several types of waypoints can be established, allowing for the ASV to move from waypoint to waypoint. Each waypoint has an attached behaviour, for example the ASV can stop on them for taking measurements or to explore around them. In addition, some typical exploratory operations, such as a lawn-mow trajectory in a rectangular area, can be concisely specified (e.g., by just setting the corners of the rectangle). Moreover, the ASVs behaviour can be guided by more complex algorithms, such as those summarized in the following sections. Finally, note that all this functional flexibility represents an original contribution of our research, compared with existing commercial ASVs.

Simulation-based ASVs path planning

In certain cases, no information on suspicious biological activity is available in each water body, and a systematic exploration is in order (such as the zig-zag trajectory presented in Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Systematic exploration of a reservoir.

However, completely blind explorations could be avoided by means of exploiting the local history of previous events or the clues provided by simulations. In other words,

we can send the ASVs toward the places of interest, according to available information, and ensure that they are reached at the appropriate times.

We have developed a simulation prototype for demonstrating how this could be useful for planning the path of the ASV, by combining the predictions of a HAB simulator and an effective optimization of different aspects of the mission.

Supposing that a certain population of algae is initially located at a region of the water body, our simulator determines the evolution of the 3D distribution and concentration of this population, in function of biological growth, light intensity at different depths, and water currents. To do it, we first simulate the water currents and next the dispersion and growth of a bloom represented by a set of particles. For illustrating this process, on one hand, figure 4 shows, using warmer colors for higher values, the speeds only at the surface of a water body (with a surface area of $3.17 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^2$ and a maximum depth of 100 m) that is under a certain water inflow and outflow. On the other one, figure 5 summarizes the evolution of the algae population, whose initial location (at $t = 0$) is represented by the set of red particles displayed at the image in the left-hand side and whose final situation (including population growth), after 56 h, is displayed at the image in the right hand.

Once the simulation is accomplished, we optimize, using evolutionary algorithms, a 3D trajectory for the ASV and its probe depth, to ensure that it can get as many useful measurements as possible, while minimizing the mission duration and trajectory length. Figure 6 shows in black the optimized

Fig. 4. Surface speeds of the flow simulation of a particular water body with inflow and outflow.

Fig. 5. Algae population evolution after 56 hours.

Fig. 6. ASV trajectory optimization for getting useful data while the HAB evolves and move.

trajectory of the ASV. On its right hand, the traces of the HAB area sensed by the ASV, after having travelled the whole trajectory, are highlighted in green. See (Carazo-Barbero *et al.*, 2021) for more details.

Sensor-driven ASV control

In practice, when no other information is available, it could be useful for the ASVs to use their sensors for detecting the algae, and move towards locations of maximum concentration, or follow a contour of the algae bloom. To illustrate this idea, figure 7 showed a bloom on the sea, where we have marked a contour with a yellow-ellipse a maximum with a red-dot.

Fig. 7. A bloom on the sea; we marked a contour.

For driving towards a maximum, we successfully tried the Nelder-Mead SIMPLEX algorithm, which is used in numerical optimization of 2D functions. The algorithm departs from three points forming a triangle. A systematic procedure is followed to substitute the worst vertex for a new one, selected among four possible cases. A series of triangles is obtained, with the triangles moving towards the maximum, expanding towards better areas, encircling the maximum, and shrinking around it.

To obtain the maximum, we translate each vertex to a waypoint for ASV motion on water. The value at the vertex is the measurement that the ASV takes at the waypoint. Therefore, the ASV will move according to the algorithm while gathering measurements that will be used to decide the next movement. Figure 8 shows, in red, the trajectory followed by the ASV in simulation, considering a bivariate Gaussian distribution of the algae population. The colours in the legend of figure 8 can be used to identify each of the triangles created by the SIMPLEX algorithm.

To determine the contour, we use the PAT algorithm, which is even simpler. Basically, it builds a triangular grid around the contour, considering only if the measurements taken at the two last visited vertexes of the grid are both inside, both outside or one inside and the other outside of the contour level. Figure 9 shows the result of a simulation with this approach.

Results and Discussion

Although part of this research is in a preliminary stage, good results in simulation have been obtained. We have also made experiments with one of the ASVs, on a river, for functional study in the presence of potential users. See (Besada-Portas *et al.*, 2021) for more details

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Fig. 8. Basic concept of the SIMPLEX algorithm.

Fig. 9. ASV locating the maximum guided by the SIMPLEX algorithm.

Fig. 10. ASV determining a contour guided by the PAT algorithm.

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